

A framework for data-driven decision support for operational planning in active distribution networks

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Abstract

This paper describes a framework envisioned to be part of operational planning to help Distribution System Operators (DSOs) securely operate the grid. The main two components of the framework are workflows for grid situational awareness and dynamic tariffs for implicit control of demand and distributed generation. Digital Twins (DT) and Internet of Things (IoT) technologies are leveraged to compose a modular framework to execute specific workflows aimed at increasing the observability of the grid state and to analyse the impact of dynamic tariffs on alleviating grid violations. Data analytics and grid modelling are applied to assimilate data, detect anomalies either due to incipient grid faults or demand and generation irregularities, calculate power flows, estimate the risk of grid violations such as cable overloading, and aid the design of effective grid tariffs. In addition to presenting the concept of the AISOP project, the Digital Process Twin (DPT) framework, progress on anomaly detection and power flow forecasting is presented, and an outlook on implementation aspects is given.

1 Introduction

In this work, the vision of decision support for operational planning in distribution systems has two pillars: situational awareness and non-intrusive decision support tools in the form of temporal and spatial dynamic tariffs.

1.1 Digitalisation in power systems

The prospect of digitalisation of medium voltage (MV) and low voltage (LV) grids encompasses sensors, actuators, and grid topology data, as well as the assimilation of these data into decision-making. In this context, DTs have a significant potential to facilitate grid operation by providing static and dynamic information about the grid that can be used to automate processes or to simulate scenarios with the objective of facilitating tasks of human operators. Updated data is an essential input to DTs, which means that the Information and Communications Technology (ICT) and data management systems play an important role in automating the system operation. Namely, [1] points out the challenge of large amounts of data and the complexity of processing it that will come with the future digitalisation of LV grids. As digitalisation progresses, DTs can deliver value to DSOs by developing functionalities, such as real-time estimation and forecasting of grid state, into already commercialised SCADA or DMS solutions [2]. Other approaches, such as the one we pursue, are aimed at interfacing with DSO's ICT infrastructure based on standard protocols and using open-source tools,

possibly combining multiple stakeholders in the value chain of digital services for grid situational awareness and operational planning.

1.2 Grid situational awareness

DSOs usually have very limited sensors beyond distribution system substations and sometimes also insufficient information about the network to model it, resulting in limited situational awareness at the distribution system level [1, 3]. However, digitalisation is changing this situation, as shown in [3, 4], where a visualisation platform that integrates smart meter data with SCADA and grid topology data is demonstrated. Such consolidation and visualisation of data is useful as it can provide additional benefits for asset management by facilitating the analysis of complex outages and possibly reducing fault location times.

Another example is the work in [4], which shows preliminary results on a data-driven approach that maps load bus voltage changes to power flow injections. The accuracy of a linear regression model and machine learning methods are evaluated, showing that, for the selected case study, the linear regression performs better. Such an approach contributes to situational awareness, as the mapping derived between voltage and active and reactive power can be applied to estimate hosting capacity without precise knowledge of the grid.

1.3 Dynamic tariffs as implicit control

It is proven that dynamic prices of electricity can incentivise users to change their usage patterns, yielding potential benefits for DSOs. This is particularly true when full automation of energy consumption flexibility is implemented, e.g., via smart appliances and smart energy management systems [5]. More recently, [6] presents an approach that includes a qualitative assessment of grid tariffs based on questionnaires to demonstrators in different European countries. It also includes a quantitative assessment, where a DT of a demonstration case in Germany is used to simulate power flows and evaluate the impact of selected grid tariff schemes.

This paper is organised as follows. Section 2 gives an overview of the main content and approaches that are applied to develop data-driven decision support in the AI-assisted grid situational awareness and operational planning (AISOP) project. Section 3 describes preliminary results concerning anomaly detection and power flow forecasting modules. Section 4 gives an outlook into implementations with different project partners and the next development steps.

2 Methodology

2.1 Digital process twin approach in AISOP

Our vision of data-driven decision support for operational planning is illustrated in Fig. 1, where the main components of a DPT are illustrated. Verified heterogeneous data sets, each with a unique identification, are an integral part of the process; they are the first step of data ingestion coming from the physical layer. The current software prototyping phase starts with data assimilation of historical data sets and grid topology data from the German utility WVN and the Swiss utility Romande Energie. Weather data is provided by the Swiss industrial partner HIVE.

The scope of the DTs for the grid congestion use case consists of Time series forecaster module, and a Grid module that includes a grid model for power flow and a model of intelligent end users, represented in the Grid DT block in Fig. 1. However, the scope and granularity can be extended to DTs of grid components such as substations, overhead lines, distribution cables, and so on. This modularity is promoted by using a Single Source of Truth (SSoT) to maintain the data collected from the physical systems (e.g., grid sensors, customers, etc.) and the data created by the DPT. The data verification process is to be maintained independently for each software module or DT.

The Knowledge Extraction block in DPT can access assimilated data and model output data from the DT (i.e., Physics and data-driven models block in Fig. 1) to perform analytics and design of dynamic tariffs. It can feed information back to the DT, particularly for the purpose of passing specifications of simulation parameters to perform scenario analysis. More importantly, it provides information to the DSO end user, in this case for the purpose of grid congestion management it delivers anomaly detection, power flow

forecast, and estimation of risk states such as line or transformer overloading, too low or too high voltage violations, and potential asset faults. Overall, the DPT supports operational planning by providing monitoring tools to improve situational awareness and the possibility of investigating the use of dynamic tariffs for implicit demand control.

Fig. 1 Block diagram of DPT with a focus on power flow, grid risk and dynamic tariffs for a grid congestion use case

2.2 Data analytics and grid modelling for situational awareness

Once the architecture of the DPT is established, we proceed to the definition of workflows (WFs) that describe sequences of processing steps and the modules involved to extract relevant information. Fig. 2 illustrates these workflows, highlighting those that are currently under development.

Sequential Power Flow Solutions WF. Involves Data Assimilation, Parsing Topology, Initialization, and Power Flow modules. Such time series-power flow approach has been extensively applied in the literature and in practice, with commercial tools offering features to load wind, solar, and load profiles to update the power flow calculation in a series of time steps to characterise the impacts of connecting more solar PV, EVs or HPs.

Power Flow Forecasting WF. Involves Data Assimilation and Time Series Forecasting modules combined with the Sequential Power Flow Solutions WF. Several approaches are under consideration, ranging from classical quantile regression, one-dimensional convolutional neural networks, and more novel and powerful deep learning (DL) architectures. As first steps, we establish a baseline for a forecast based on local linear regressions, compare power flow solutions and two

simple forecast models, a naïve one and a DL one [7,8]. These results are presented in section 3.1.

Anomaly Detection WF. Two types of anomalies are addressed: (i) grid faults (e.g., short circuits, equipment failure, incipient faults) as studied in [9]; and (ii) irregularities at the end-user side, defined as deviations from expected power quality, power consumption, or generation patterns, indicating a new and potentially unregistered demand (e.g., EV charging) or generation (e.g., solar PV). Timely detection of these abnormalities is necessary to ensure efficient energy management, prevent system failure, and optimise resource allocation. For anomaly detection at end-user side, the approach involves (ii-a) processing a large number of historical measurements at the MV-LV transformers, (ii-b) decomposing and clustering these measurements to identify typical consumption patterns within a specific group or zone, (ii-c) predicting the consumption for different seasons and days, (ii-d) detecting outliers as potential anomalies, and (ii-e) correlating these anomalies with other types of data such as solar irradiation or temperature for root-cause analysis and final identification of the cause of the anomalies. Results of an unsupervised approach to (ii-a) and (ii-d) are shown in section 3.2.

Risk Assessment WF. Involves Data assimilation, and Risk estimation, where risk is calculated dynamically every time new data is available. First, a distribution function is estimated from historical data, and a severity function defined according to the selected risk metric. The distribution function can be an empirical distribution, by simply calculating the frequency of occurrence from the data; or it can consist of fitting a probability distribution function. Several metrics are being considered but at this stage we focus on compliance to standards. Namely, supply voltage variations during normal operation: during each period of one week 95 % of the 10-min mean values shall be within +/- 10 % of the nominal voltage as specified in EN 50160. Other risk metrics currently in focus are operational Over (or Under) Voltage Risk (OVR and UVR) with exponential severity functions as described in [10]. In a second step, the distribution function is used to calculate a probability of exceedance which is then weighted by the severity function to calculate risk.

Fig. 2 Block diagram illustrating workflows for grid situational awareness based on the main software modules of the AISOP project DPT

2.3 Design of dynamic tariffs

Two dimensions are considered for the design of dynamic tariffs. One dimension is *how* tariffs are designed; the second dimension is *what* data is available to the utility. Tariffs can be designed offline for a given time span (e.g., seasonal, or annual). Alternatively, given a tariff model (e.g., a rule, or a policy parametrised with information of the grid state), tariffs can be calculated close to real-time (e.g., day-ahead, or intraday). In this case, the tariff depends more directly on grid constraints. For example, for the next day, the feed-in prices decrease if the maximum excess PV is forecasted to be above a grid constraint threshold. Regarding the data availability, three options are considered. First is the ideal case where PV generation, conventional demand, electric vehicle (EV) charging, and heat pump (HP) operation are measured at each node. A second case is a realistic future where net demand is measured at each node. A third approach is today's feasible case, where only transformer (NE6) power measurements are available. For each level of data availability, at each time step, for a selected time resolution, statistical correlation analyses are performed to identify daily/weekly/seasonal trends and dynamic retail and feed-in prices are calculated by considering the annualised cost of grid investment.

2.4 Requirements engineering and data models

By defining functional and quality requirements, as well as defining the scope of each software module and the framework, we aim at more efficient and incremental development cycles. At this stage, the focus has been on functional requirements: (i) definition of data requirements by means of creating a data catalogue that lists and describes the available sensor and model data, (ii) specification of functional requirements of each software module by defining module interfaces, and (iii) investigation of desired features and user interface. Regarding the latter, the results of an initial investigation on current practices, tools, and preferences of grid operators point to significant opportunities for digital innovation, validating the vision of the AISOP project. Namely, by applying qualitative research methods (i.e., grounded theory) to data retrieved by interviewing operators from two Swiss DSOs and the Swiss TSO, [11] finds that there are multiple potential applications for decision support tools. We summarized them as follows, in real-time operations support tools are needed to suggest grid configurations and operation actions in the case of unplanned outages and emergency situations to facilitate grid restoration to a secured alert or a normal state. In operational planning, support tools to optimise the scheduling of outage requests would make this process faster by combining grid data with operation and maintenance data. An important practical aspect is that user interface and integration of such tools into current operator workflows is key and requires a co-development process with operators.

3 Current development

3.1 Power flow forecasting

A preliminary evaluation of power flow forecaster performance is sought to gauge its feasibility. Therefore, we evaluate day-ahead power flow forecasting in terms of error propagation and computation time on 1-LV-urban6--0-sw Simbench grid. This is a radial network with 1 MV bus with a 20 to 0.4 kV transformer and 58 LV buses with 111 loads (2.0 to 31.0 kW). Simbench also includes emulated smart meter and generation data by means of generic profiles for different scenarios (i.e., today, near future, and future). First, a benchmark of a forecast is created using local linear regressions, this allows to create a simple synthetic forecast that can be arbitrarily accurate. The scenario emulated is that time series forecasts of load are issued every day at 8:00 hrs for a day-ahead. A file-based interface between the time series forecast module and the power flow solver is used at this stage and made available as an S3 bucket. The Simbench data corresponding to the generic profiles were mapped and scaled according to the grid topology, resulting in active (P) and reactive power (Q) load profiles specific to 1-LV-urban6--0-sw Simbench grid. An example is shown in the top left plot in Fig. 3, that shows time series plots of P from Load 4 and a dummy forecast issued every 24 hours. The histogram on the right shows root-mean-square error (RMSE) calculated for every day during a month for each of the 111 loads in this reference grid, mean +/- standard deviation values are shown in each for All loads, and for Load 4. The bottom plots in Fig. 3 illustrate the error between the power flow solutions calculated with the Simbench data and those calculated with the forecast.

Fig. 3 Preliminary evaluation of Power Flow Forecasting WF using a using Simbench data, a dummy load forecast, and pandapower as power flow solver

A preliminary comparison to a naïve and a DL forecast for P and Q of load 4 over a period of one month is presented in Table 1. The naïve model is an average of past data, and the

DL model is a pretrained Text-to-Text transformer, T5 architecture with 8M parameters, used as a zero-shot inference tool, without fine tuning. For both models the input is data of the three previous days as illustrated in Fig. 4. Although, as shown in Table 1, the DL forecast has a mean RMSE lower than the naïve forecast, its standard deviation is significantly larger. Both the naïve and the DL forecast can be easily improved, and more extensive comparisons will be performed.

Table 1 Comparison of daily RMSE

	Dummy	Naïve	T5 zero-shot
P [kW]	0.610	1.504	1.281
	± 0.386	± 0.771	± 1.153
Q [kVAr]	0.398	0.737	0.692
	± 0.323	± 0.397	± 0.544

Fig. 4 Example of load forecasting with naïve and deep learning models

3.2 Anomaly detection

Processing large amounts of grid monitoring data and detecting points that are different to the bulk is a first step towards identifying potential issues. Particularly challenging can be to develop reliable algorithms without ground truth data to train them and to evaluate their performance. In such situations, statistics, unsupervised learning, and domain knowledge can be applied. As illustrated in Fig. 5, unsupervised learning can support DSO analysts to filter data and identify periods where disturbances occur. Anomalous data is detected within data recorded between October 2018 to December 2019, every 10-min, by a grid monitoring device installed at the LV side of a distribution transformer operated by Romande Energie. The dataset includes 58 quantities that describe voltage, power, current, harmonics, and grid frequency.

The first step is pre-processing (i.e., removing the mean, scaling to unit variance, removing linear correlations), then dimension reduction (e.g., in this case by applying singular value decomposition the dataset with 58 quantities can be reduced to one with 15 components that explain 95 % of the variance). A final step is to find those data points that are most different to the majority (e.g., in this case by applying a density based clustering method and manipulating two hyperparameters: a distance to neighbour threshold, and a number of samples around a cluster center). Fig. 5 shows two clusters of points on a principal components-plane, one corresponds to a normal behaviour, and the other to odd values that might represent an anomaly. Namely, three of these points

are highlighted and mapped to the original time series, where the distortion in the voltage can be appreciated leading to an understanding of the root-cause.

Fig. 5 First two principal components (top plot) and time series (bottom plots) of grid monitoring data, showing identified anomalies

4 Outlook

Increasing digitisation and digitalization of the physical infrastructure and the grid operation and planning processes will expedite the secure integration of new electrical demand (i.e., EV charging, HPs) and new distributed generation (e.g., solar PVs at LV). The efficient acquisition and processing of heterogeneous types of data are essential to identify the challenges of grid hosting capacities and to take techno-economic measures. The use of IoT to effectively collect data and DPTs with advanced analytics to derive knowledge from the collected data to support DSO daily operations has multiple use cases.

In the AISOP project, a DPT with SSoT facilitates the management of data from IoT sensors and model outputs. Workflows for forecasting the grid state and risks by performing data analytics are envisioned to support decision-making. These workflows will be applied to design dynamic grid tariffs, which can motivate end-users to change their consumption patterns or generation outputs. This approach is especially practical and important when proliferation of EVs and solar PVs is faster than the realisation of grid expansion. Dynamic grid tariffs for demand and generation, separately,

are easier to implement in LV grids compared to market mechanisms, such as peer-to-peer energy trading, flexibility markets, etc. Thus, dynamic tariffs have the potential to immediately help the grid operators to defer grid investments.

Given the proposed DPT architecture and workflows, implementations are possible via marketplaces for software applications or with tighter integrations in commercial tools. As illustrated in Fig. 6. where, for the different data sources and use cases in Germany (top blocks) and Switzerland (bottom blocks), the flow of data from sources to software applications is shown. The blocks **Logarithmo** (data clean up, storage, transformation) and **HSLU** (data assimilation) consolidate and prepare the data by performing identification of missing data, data type validation checks, amongst other data quality checks. The goal is to provide a central point of access to data, facilitating that DPTs access it, ensuring data integrity and governance to achieve SSoT.

Next steps in our development, include extending some of the analyses presented to data from two sites in Switzerland to illustrate how better monitoring and risk forecasting can support DSO decisions. Followed by the integration of risk metrics into the design of dynamic tariffs to facilitate the evaluation of different tariff schemes.

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Fig. 6 Illustration of data flows from sources to platforms for commercial implementation

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